

Appendix B

Table 1. Quality assessment.

#	Question	Answer and score
QA1	Does the study present topics about	Agree (+1)
	pre-trained models of Natural	Partially (0)
	Processing Language in the pictograms?	Disagree (-1)
QA2	Does the study present	Agree (+1)
	issues about pictograms	Partially (0)
	and data science?	Disagree (-1)
QA3	Has the study been	Very relevant (+1)
	published in a relevant journal	Relevant (0)
	or conference?	Not relevant (-1)
QA4	Has the study	Yes, more than 5 (+1)
	been cited by	Partially, from 1 to 5 (0)
	other authors	No, it has not (-1)

Fig. 1. Normalization applied in pictogram taxonomies.

Fig. 2. Processing techniques used in pictograms.

Fig. 3. Methodologies hired in analysis models.

Fig. 4. Data science algorithms applied in analysis models.

Fig. 5. Algorithms used in data normalization techniques.

Fig. 6. Data analysis models and data normalization techniques.

Fig. 7. Data mining techniques in different study types.

Fig. 8. Evaluation of algorithms in diverse research types.